

EVALUATION OF THE COMBINATION OF RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCES IN AN OFFSHORE PLATFORM, USING TOPSIS MULTICRITERIA METHOD

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Keywords: Multi-Use Platform, Renewable Energy Sources, MCDA techniques, TOPSIS Multi-criteria, MUSICA project.

Abstract

Combining different renewable energy sources increases electricity production and system availability. In this paper, the risks arising from interconnection of subsystems with different technologies in a floating multi-use platform are assessed through the application of the TOPSIS multicriteria method. The different renewable energy subsystems are evaluated in different operational conditions either stand-alone or in combination. The application aims to achieve the quantification of benefits of the combination of a wind turbine, photovoltaic panels, wave energy converters, and energy storage subsystems on board an offshore floating platform using the proposed method as an assessment tool. Finally, the most suitable sites for installing the overall structure are evaluated through the Analytic Hierarchy Process.

1 Introduction

The MUSICA (Multiple Use of Space for Island Clean Autonomy) solution [1] is a decarbonizing one-stop shop for small islands and their Blue Growth initiatives. The MUSICA project develops the platform that will be installed in the coastal area of Oinousses Island in Greece. It will provide a full suite of Blue Growth solutions including three forms of Renewable Energy (RE): wind, solar, and wave, innovative energy storage systems on the MultiUse Platform (MUP), smart energy system in combination with the island grid, desalinated water, and green support services for the island's aquaculture (Figure 1). The overall aim is to accelerate the development of its MUP and Multi-Use of Space (MUS) combination for the small island needs, and de-risk future operators. Innovative energy storage systems on the MUP provide all the required energy, as well as electrical output

smoothing through compressed water/air storage and batteries. The floating structure has been developed in such a way that the energy required for producing water by a reverse osmosis desalination unit, the electricity for feeding and the management of the aquaculture, as well as the power for resident needs is supplied from the installed renewable energy systems, which utilize the abundant RES potential of the region. The combination of the different power subsystems is expected to increase the operational period of the reverse osmosis system as well as the electricity production.

Figure 1. MUSICA Platform

Hence many factors are evaluated each time for the effectiveness of the overall system and the implementation of the appropriate technology. The TOPSIS methodology is proposed as an effective evaluation tool in order to meet the different criteria related to the reliability, consumer needs and energy production demand.

The Multi-Criteria-Decision-Making (MCDM) TOPSIS methodology uses decision matrixes formed with weights that were carried out from design and operational characteristics. In order to evaluate the utilization of the different renewable energy production systems, data for each technology is compared with others. By normalizing these data, the weight of each criterion matrix is formed, which is inserted in alternatives evaluation matrix. The value of each alternative in

relation with each criterion is evaluated and separately introduced and normalized by suitable weights.

Many European islands are not able to adopt RES and desalination on their island, nor deploy aquaculture near shore, due to spatial and environmental reasons. MUSICA will consider the island inhabitants and the sea-based MUP consumers, evaluate the technological, environmental, economic and spatial aspects and criteria to make this new offshore MUP approach a win-win situation for every stakeholder; either producer or user. In this context, the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) is also used, as one of multi-criteria methods, to assign weights of importance in each evaluation criterion and finally find the most suitable sites for the placement of the structure.

In this paper, the following sections discuss the overall methodology for evaluation of reliability of the structure through TOPSIS multi-criteria method, as well as site suitability analysis through AHP. Conclusions and findings are summarized in the last section.

2 Methodological framework

The proposed methodological framework is divided into two (2) parts: a) coastal and marine spatial suitability assessment, and b) reliability assessment of the structure, both using Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) techniques. The processing steps are described below.

2.1 Description of the methodology of site selection

2.1.1 Overview

The siting process is a multi-criteria decision analysis problem that takes into consideration a set of attributes that determines the suitability of a site. These attributes include constraints that can be technical, economic, environmental, cultural and spatial, and criteria by which a particular site can be evaluated as more preferable than another. The constraints and evaluation criteria determine the selection of potential sites. The AHP is used to assign weights of importance in each evaluation criterion. The AHP originally developed by Saaty (1980) is one of the most important representatives of MCDA techniques and its implementation is very often in the international literature in site selection issues [2, 3, 4, 5, 6]. The wide use of AHP compared to other MCDA techniques is attributed to the fact that it can take into account quantitative as well as qualitative criteria and factors [7].

2.2.2 Evaluation of possible installation sites

There are six (6) possible sites for the MUSICA MUP. Five (5) of them are near Oinousses and one (1) near Chios Island (Greece) (Figure 2). The MUSICA platform is considered a flexible and advanced solution that can be installed in small islands and cover the needs for water and energy supply. The six (6) possible sites selected combine the following advantages:

- Favourable wind and wave conditions;
- Demand for energy and water supply;

- Proximity to already installed aquaculture facilities;
- Minimize investment, maintenance and operation costs;
- Maximize local acceptance;

Figure 2. The suitable sites for the MUP installation

- Do not fall under any constraint (e.g. use of sea space by other users).

It is important to note that the MUP will be installed in the proximity of sites (x,y coordinates), and for this reason, a buffer zone of 400 m from each point is identified.

In order to select one of them, this stage of methodology accepts that there are graduations in the six (6) suitability sites, which arise from the evaluation of the sites in a number of factors, i.e. Evaluation criteria. Eleven (11) evaluation criteria are determined based on the literature review and expert judgments through interviews and discussions, as follows:

- *Wind potential (WP)*: one of the most important factors, as it determines the percentage of electricity produced at each site.
- *Wave potential (WaP)*: it also determines the percentage of electricity produced at each site.
- *Distance from electricity grid (DFEG)*: an extremely important factor for technical and economic reasons. Sites that are closer to existing or under development electricity grid are preferable.
- *Distance from water supply network (DFWS)*: similar to electricity grid, sites that are closer to water supply network are preferable.
- *Distance from aquaculture facilities (DFAF)*: sites closer to aquaculture facilities are preferable.
- *Permissions (PER)*: what is the feeling about the ease of obtaining permits.
- *Accessibility (ACC)*: During the project development and trials phase visits to MUP will be frequent. Easy accessibility to the location by boat is important.
- *Bathymetry & Sea bottom Soil (BATH & SBS)*: are important for the anchoring of the MUP. Mainly a technical/economic criterion, since great depths and sea bottom soil, could lead to higher installation costs.
- *Distance from settlements (DFS)*: distance reduces visual and noise disturbance that results from facility operation and ensure the social acceptance by local community.

- Distance from areas of particular environmental interest (DFPA): The Natura areas cover 19% of the Greek territory. Obviously, this does not mean that the economic activity stops in all these areas. There are procedures by the Greek law for the licensing of several activities inside Natura. However, the conservation as long as possible distances from these areas is considered very important.

2.2.3 The Analytic Hierarchy Process

Furthermore, the eleven (11) evaluation criteria may not be equally important, so the most important criteria are weighted with a higher weight than the others. This is achieved through the development of a pair-wise comparison matrix in AHP.

First stage of AHP is the development of hierarchical structure of the site selection problem, where the general objective of the problem is located at the top level, the eleven (11) evaluation criteria at the second level, and the six (6) possible sites at the lower level (Figure 3).

Second stage is the development of the pair-wise comparison matrix of evaluation criteria according to the nine point scale of Saaty (Table 1) [8]. Through the pair-wise comparison the preferences of analysts involved in the decision making process are decoded and incorporated into the modelling.

Figure 3. Hierarchical structure of siting of MUP

Table 1. The nine-point scale of AHP

If the criterion A is.....compared to B:	Then the corresponding preference number is:
1	Equal importance
3	Moderate importance
5	Strong importance
7	Very strong importance
9	Extreme importance
2,4,6,8	Intermediate values between two adjacent judgments

Third stage is the calculation of the weights of the eleven (11) evaluation criteria, including a number of sub-steps. The weights of evaluation criteria, as resulted from the above steps are presented in Table 2.

Last stage of AHP is the calculation of Consistency Ration (CR). The calculation of CR is particularly useful, as it ensures

that the judgments/opinions taken into account were correct. The overall procedure is presented as follows: Initially, the Consistency Index (CI) is calculated from the following formula:

$$CI = \frac{\lambda_{max} - n}{n - 1} = \frac{11.31 - 11}{11 - 1} = 0.031 \quad (1)$$

where n is the number of criteria and λ_{max} is the maximum eigenvalue. Finally, the CI is calculated as follows:

$$CR = \frac{CI}{RI} = \frac{0.031}{1.51} = 0.021 \quad (2)$$

where the RI is the Random Consistency Index of a random-like matrix [8]. The value of CR should be no higher than 0.1.

2.2.4 Classification of possible sites & results

Eleven (11) evaluation criteria were determined based on literature review and experts' opinion [3, 6, 10]. In order to be combined these different criteria, a common measurement scale should be predefined. Each evaluation criterion takes value from 0 (restricted/inappropriate areas) to 6. The higher the value of suitability scale, the more attractive is the criterion value. This method is based on the "Maximum score procedure" [9] and is described for each evaluation criterion in the following table (Table 2).

Table 2. Suitability classes of evaluation criteria

Evaluation criterion	Weight (%)	Field	Scale Value		
Mean wind speed (m/sec)					
WP	25	≥ 5.000001	6		
		4.000001-5	5		
		3.000001-4	4		
		2.000001-3	1		
		1.000001-2	0		
(m)					
DFEG	17.5	0-500	6		
		501-1000	5		
		1001-1500	4		
		1501-2000	3		
		2001-2500	2		
ACC	17.5	≥ 2501	1		
		(m)			
		0-500	6		
		501-1000	5		
		1001-1500	4		
DFWS	12	1501-2000	3		
		2001-2500	2		
		≥ 2501	1		
		(m)			
		0-500	1		
DFS	9	501-1000	2		
		1001-1500	3		
		1501-2000	4		

Evaluation criterion (Cont.)	Weight (%)	Field	2001-2500	5
			≥ 2501	6
PER	6	(Type)		
		Very easy	6	
		Easy	5	
		Moderate	4	
		Somewhat hard	3	
		Hard	2	
DFAF	4.5	Very hard	1	
		(m)		
		0-500	6	
		501-1000	5	
		1001-1500	4	
		1501-2000	3	
WaP	3	2001-2500	2	
		≥ 2501	1	
		(m)		
		Mean significant wave height (m)		
		0.5000001-0.6	6	
		0.4000001-0.5	5	
DFPA	2.5	0.3000001-0.4	4	
		0.2000001-0.3	3	
		0.1000001-0.2	2	
		(m)		
		In Natura areas	3	
		Out Natura areas	6	
BATH	1.5	(m)		
		0-30	1	
		31-60	6	
		61-100	3	
SBS	1.5	(Type of substrate)		
		Rocky	6	
		Sandy/Muddy	0	

During the development phase of the structure, the optimization goals were to minimize movements and loads from waves, improve the operation conditions for all components and withstand extreme weather conditions. In this regard, no restrictions are applied on the mean significant wave height to exclude some possible locations.

In the Table 3 the values of each evaluation criterion of the six possible sites are listed. In the last stage of the methodology, the value of each possible site (after standardization), will be multiplied by the corresponding weight of the criterion. The weighted possible sites are summed to develop a total score (Overall Suitability Index-OSI) for each site (Table 4).

Table 3. Values for each evaluation criterion of possible sites

	Site 1	Site 2	Site 3	Site 4	Site 5	Site 6
WP	5	5	6	5	6	6
DFEG	4	5	3	4	4	3
ACC	5	5	3	4	4	2
DFWS	5	4	3	4	4	2
DFS	2	3	5	3	5	6
PER	2	4	5	4	4	4
DFAF	1	1	5	5	4	5
WaP	5	4	6	4	6	6
DFPA	6	3	6	3	6	6
BATH	6	1	3	1	6	6
SBS	6	6	6	6	6	6

Table 4. Overall Suitability Index of possible sites

Crit.	Weight Factor (%)	Site 1	Site 2	Site 3	Site 4	Site 5	Site 6
WP	25	1.25	1.25	1.5	1.25	1.5	1.5
DFEG	17.5	0.7	0.875	0.525	0.875	0.875	0.525
ACC	17.5	0.875	0.875	0.525	0.7	0.7	0.35
DFWS	12	0.6	0.48	0.36	0.48	0.48	0.24
DFS	9	0.18	0.27	0.45	0.27	0.45	0.54
PER	6	0.12	0.24	0.3	0.24	0.24	0.24
DFAF	4.5	0.045	0.045	0.225	0.225	0.18	0.225
WaP	3	0.15	0.12	0.18	0.12	0.18	0.18
DFPA	2.5	0.15	0.075	0.15	0.075	0.15	0.15
BATH	1.5	0.09	0.015	0.045	0.015	0.09	0.09
SBS	1.5	0.09	0.09	0.09	0.09	0.09	0.09
OSI	-	4.25	4.335	4.35	4.34	4.935	4.13

Figure 4. Most suitable site for MUP siting

The most suitable site for MUP siting is the Site 5, as it presents the highest Overall suitability index (Table 4, Figure 4). The rest sites are equally suitable, having however more “drawbacks”, i.e. higher visual impact, harder licensing process, greater distances for connecting to grids, etc. but within acceptable limits. Although only 0-scale values are characterized as unsuitable areas (i.e. excluded from the analysis), low-scale values are not preferred.

Apart from advantageous wind and wave potential, Site 5 has favourable economics due to its closeness to electricity grid and water supply network. It is also characterized by easier licensing process, greater accessibility and proximity to aquaculture facilities, while minimizing visual and noise disturbance and ensuring social acceptance by the local community.

3 Data Analysis and evaluation model

In order to evaluate the different technologies installed on MUP platform [11] or the effectiveness of the combination of renewable energy production systems each technology is studied and evaluated compared with the rest [12], [13], [14].

The imported data are the results of operational and qualitative data of determination of other pilot systems with equivalent characteristics for each technology. So, the conclusions could reflect the implementation of technologies in MUP platform according to different criteria.

The criteria weighted by selection of beneficiaries and non-beneficiaries randomly, to represents the different opinions and concerns [15]. These weights are used to solve the decision matrices of alternatives selection and criteria with the TOPSIS method. The criteria and the impact of each criterion for the selection of appropriate alternative, related to:

- The Reliability (R) of each system to produce power during operation with the lowest down time period, due to the weather conditions in installation area and the exploitation of energy even during night time.
- The Coverage of Consumer Needs (CCN) which includes the risks posed by a potential failure of a system, the visual annoyance, and the impact on marine traffic, so long as the needs of water production is related to insular areas.
- The Relative Performance (RP) which compares the systems availability in energy production and interconnection with desalination system.
- The Probability of Down Time Period (PDTP) during energy demand according to the inherent natural variability of weather conditions.
- The Engineering Difficulty (ED) or complexity, which is related to the installation difficulties in the interconnection of the different technologies as well as the availability of spare parts, the manpower required to carry out repairs in the event of a breakdown and planned maintenance work.

The alternatives used to evaluate the selection of the best technology, or the suitable combination are the following: wind turbine (WT), photovoltaic panels (PV), wave energy system (WES), energy storage subsystems (ESS), and systems interconnection (SI).

The TOPSIS method was selected for this assessment as a method of compensatory aggregation that compares a set of alternatives by setting the weights for each criterion, normalizing the scores for each criterion, and calculating the geometric distance between each alternative and the ideal alternative that represents the best score for each criterion.

4 Technique for order preference by similarity to ideal solution (TOPSIS)

In order to introduce an evaluation tool for decision makers, which could analyze the requirements an offshore renewable energy production system the tool of Technique for order preference by similarity to ideal solution (TOPSIS) is proposed.

The TOPSIS method was introduced by Hwang and Yoon in 1981 with further developments by Yoon in 1987 [8] and is based on the idea that the best alternative should have the shortest distance from the positive ideal solution and farthest distance from the negative ideal solution. TOPSIS is a multiple

criteria decision making (MCDM) method to identify solutions from a finite set of alternatives.

The procedure in using TOPSIS is the following: First define the alternatives to be evaluated. Then define the decision criteria to be evaluated by beneficiaries and non-beneficiaries' opinions or the ones that have been taken as results of another evaluation methodology [16] [17]. The responses of beneficiaries and the collected quantified data are translated into a score via the use of discrete 9-point scales.

Table 4. The scores that assumed are inserted in a matrix.

Intensity of value.	Value description
1	Not preferred - Not important
3	slightly more preferred/ important
5	strongly preferred/important
7	very strongly preferred/important
9	absolutely preferred- important
2,4,6,8	When a compromise in evaluation is needed

Then TOPSIS method evaluates the decision matrix $X = [x_{ij}]_{m \times n}$ which refers to m alternatives which are evaluated in terms of n criteria and denotes the performance measure of the i^{th} alternative in terms of the j^{th} criterion. Its steps are as follows:

Step 1. Calculate the normalized decision matrix $R = [r_{ij}]_{m \times n}$ where m is the number of alternatives and n is the number of criteria. The normalized value r_{ij} is calculated as:

$$r_{ij} = \frac{x_{ij}}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^m x_{ij}^2}} \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m; j = 1, 2, \dots, n$$

The normalization is done for convenience of comparison by converting different units of criteria to a unified unit.

Step 2. Calculate the weighted normalized decision matrix $V = [v_{ij}]_{m \times n}$. The weighted normalized value is calculated as

$$v_{ij} = (w_j)(r_{ij}) \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m; j = 1, 2, \dots, n$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^n w_j = 1$$

where w_j is the weight of the j^{th} criterion and

Step 3. Determine the positive ideal solution (PIS) A^+ and negative ideal solution (NIS) A^- :

$$A^+ = \left\{ \left(\max_i v_{ij} | j \in J \right), \left(\min_i v_{ij} | j \in J' \right) | i = 1, 2, \dots, m \right\} = \{v_1^+, v_2^+, \dots, v_j^+, \dots, v_n^+\}$$

$$A^- = \left\{ \left(\min_i v_{ij} | j \in J \right), \left(\max_i v_{ij} | j \in J' \right) | i = 1, 2, \dots, m \right\} = \{v_1^-, v_2^-, \dots, v_j^-, \dots, v_n^-\}$$

where $J = \{j = 1, 2, \dots, n | j \text{ associated with the criteria having a positive impact}\}$

$J' = \{j = 1, 2, \dots, n | j \text{ associated with the criteria having a negative impact}\}$

Step 4. Calculate the separation measures, using the n -dimensional Euclidean distance.

The separation of each alternative from the positive ideal solution:

$$S_i^+ = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (v_{ij} - v_j^+)^2} \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m$$

The separation of each alternative from the negative ideal solution:

$$S_i^- = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (v_{ij} - v_j^-)^2} \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m$$

Step 5. Calculate the relative closeness to the ideal solution:

$$P = \frac{S_i^-}{(S_i^+ + S_i^-)}, 0 < c < 1, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m$$

$$P_i = 1 \quad \text{if } A_i = A^+$$

$$P_i = 0 \quad \text{if } A_i = A^-$$

Step 6. Rank the alternatives with respect to P_i in the descending order. The preferred alternative should have the shortest distance from the positive ideal solution and the farthest distance from the negative ideal solution, where a higher c_i would mean higher preference.

5 The Development of TOPSIS

The decision matrix for the TOPSIS methodology was formed with the weights that were carried out from expert's opinion. As described in 3 and 4 paragraph the stakeholders from different sectors, in this case offshore structures engineers, investors, and habitats, evaluate the criteria. By normalization of these data, the weight of each criterion matrix Table 5 and 6 is constructed. The score of each alternative in relation with each criterion evaluated by experts is normalized by criterion weights to the Decision matrix Table 7.

Then the method determines the positive and negative ideal solution Table 8, and computes the separation measures, the relative closeness to the ideal solution and finally the distance from the positive ideal solution and the farthest distance from the negative ideal solution of the preferred alternative. Additionally, in Table 8 the Performance Score is calculated and shows the rank for each alternative.

Table 5. Decision matrix with criterion values for each alternative.

		<i>Criteria</i>				
		R	CCN	RP	PDTP	ED
<i>Alternatives</i>	WT	9	7	8	7	8
	PV	9	3	8	7	9
	WES	7	2	6	4	7
	ESSS	7	2	7	7	8
	SI	8	9	9	9	8

Table 6. Calculate Normalized Matrix.

		<i>Criteria</i>				
		R	CCN	RP	PDTP	ED
<i>Alternatives</i>	WT	0,50000	0,57735	0,46657	0,44813	0,44582
	PV	0,50000	0,24744	0,46657	0,44813	0,50155
	WES	0,38889	0,16496	0,34993	0,25607	0,39009
	ESS	0,38889	0,16496	0,40825	0,44813	0,44582
	SI	0,44444	0,74231	0,52489	0,57617	0,44582

Table 7. Calculated weighted Normalised Matrix with criterion weights for each alternative relative to stakeholders weighting of each attribute.

		<i>Criteria</i>				
		R	CCN	RP	PDTP	ED
<i>Alternatives</i>	WT	0,10000	0,14434	0,04666	0,13444	0,06687
	PV	0,10000	0,06186	0,04666	0,13444	0,07523
	WES	0,07778	0,04124	0,03499	0,07682	0,05851
	ESS	0,07778	0,04124	0,04082	0,13444	0,06687
	SI	0,08889	0,18558	0,05249	0,17285	0,06687

Table 8. Matrix with results of Calculation of Euclidean distance from the positive and negative ideal solution, and the relative closeness to the ideal solution

I	S_i^+	S_i^-	P_i	Rank
WT	0,03516	0,07772	0,68851	2
PV	0,08769	0,06134	0,41159	3
WES	0,12353	0,03596	0,22547	5
ESS	0,10268	0,05650	0,35495	4
SI	0,00591	0,13369	0,95765	1

In the implementation of TOPSIS method and the results obtained is defined quantitative that the best solution in respect to the relative closeness to ideal solution under the proposed criteria and the relative evaluation, and the systems interconnection enhanced for MUP platform operational conditions.

According to the results in Table 8 from the application of the TOPSIS methodology, the use of energy generated by the interconnection of systems creates more security and reliability in energy supply. This energy is provided as electrical power to both on-platform consumptions such as the reverse osmosis unit and the small-scale aquaculture unit. In addition, the interconnection of the systems for power generation also reduces the possibility of power supply interruption of the percentage of the power supplied to the island grid.

Next to interconnection, the most reliable source for power generation is the wind turbine, since due to the founded location it delivers electric power with fewer interruptions in its operation.

Photovoltaic panels while being a reliable source of electrical power, due to the limitation in output from the variation in daylight, as well as the reduction in electrical power output in different seasons are the third most ideal solution. On the other hand, energy storage systems as the fourth and wave energy systems as the fifth ideal solution contribute to system availability but are the least efficient in terms of overall system performance and their contribution to system interconnection.

Conclusions

In this paper an innovative methodology based on MCDA techniques is utilised in order to combine the different criteria

related to reliability, consumer needs, energy production versus demand and site suitability for a multi-use offshore platform.

The research for improving the closeness coefficient from the initial combination to the optimal parameter combination with TOPSIS provides a result for the optimum management of RES exploitation systems that the platform consists of and observes how improvements in the performance characteristics can be achieved. Initially different installation places and system configurations were examined and evaluated. Future research will apply this methodology utilizing also operational data in addition to design characteristics and simulations.

The results of the proposed methodology showed that Site 5 is more suitable compared to the other five (5) sites due to the most favourable characteristics at a total level (i.e. higher OSI). The other sites can be characterized as equally suitable having however more drawbacks, but within acceptable thresholds. However, the evaluation of emerging sites together with field research and examination of all individual parameters at a local scale are considered important in order to make the final choice.

The presented methodology could be adopted by decision-makers and other involved groups in order to find suitable locations for the installation of multi-use platforms in the coastal and marine areas of the Greek territory. However, the proposed model can be used to assess suitability of offshore locations for the siting of any offshore energy structure, as it is extremely flexible and incorporates a variety of exclusion or/and evaluation criteria.

Acknowledgements

This research is part of the MUSICA Project funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 862252.

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